

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue III, March 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

**WORLD
EDUCATION
CONNECT**

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

San Lorenzo Unified School District
Educational Services Department
Data, Assessment and Inquiry Division

**DEVELOPMENTAL BIBLIOTHERAPY IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION:
ASSESSING ITS IMPACT AS AN INTERVENTION FOR PROMOTING SOCIAL
AND EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN YOUNG CHILDREN**

RONALD FLORES PASCUA, Ph.D.
Certificated Education Specialist M/S
Dayton School
March 2024

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT **Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

INTRODUCTION

Problem Identification and Formulation

Social-emotional development starts the moment a child is born. Studies reveal that infants are prepared to interact with others in their surroundings from birth. Learning pathways to the brain are created when a child's physical and emotional requirements are satisfied. These pathways enable learning in all developmental areas. Social cues like laughing, sobbing, or expressing interest and focus can have a big impact on how other people behave. Children's social behaviors are also influenced by other people's emotional responses. As kids grow older and mature, their social-emotional abilities shift from being primarily focused on having their parents and guardians meet their needs to be more focused on following routines and having fun with friends and family.

Emotions shape who we are, how we pay attention, remember things, and learn new things, how we build relationships, and how our physical and mental health. They also have an impact on our acts, behaviors, and social interactions. Our perception of others and our feelings about ourselves are based on our social-emotional development. Our foundation starts the moment we are born and keeps growing over the course of our lives. The quality of a child's relationships with his primary caregivers has the biggest impact on his social-emotional development.

A child's social-emotional development is greatly influenced by early relationships and experiences that are supportive and loving. They also affect the early child's brain development. A child's early years are crucial for the development of an attachment relationship, which is long-lasting. It is based on the infant and primary caregiver's frequent encounters. The infant's attempts to become physically and emotionally close to the caregiver, as well as the caregiver's reactions to these attempts, are the key subjects of these interactions. Their impact endures, shaping the child's self-perception, thoughts, and interactions with the outside world, as well as his expectations of others (Reinsberg, 2020).

Within the framework of their relationships with main caregivers, as well as within their families and cultures, children acquire social-emotional abilities. Think about how varied our society is. It makes sense that families from various cultures would teach their kids how to interact with people, control their emotions, and interact with others in a variety of ways. For instance, youngsters are encouraged to avoid making eye contact in some cultures. In other cultures, making eye contact is a necessary part of interacting with others. Parenting styles and the ways in which people are trained to manage their emotions, particularly stress and hardship, are also influenced by culture.

Preschoolers learn to share toys and materials, play close to one another, converse with peers, take turns, and express their own and other people's feelings. They also start to autonomously follow schedules at home and in the classroom. Youngsters pick up social skills through talks with peers and adults as well as through observing others in action. If preschool teachers involve their young charges in meaningful interactions

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

**WORLD
EDUCATION
CONNECT**
MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

with peers and other adults in the classroom and program from an early age, they will be better able to develop their social-emotional abilities.

A person's ability to learn and their general development are impacted by their social-emotional health. Studies reveal that kids with good social-emotional health are generally happier, more eager to learn, have a better attitude toward school, are more likely to participate in class activities, and perform better academically than their less socially and emotionally mature peers. As a result, children's physical and social-emotional wellbeing are of equal importance. Social-emotional abilities are essential to children's physical health, self-expression, learning, and relationship development since they have a direct impact on the growth of young children in the long run. In healthy children, social-emotional stages develop on an expected trajectory, and monitoring these milestones is an imperative part of preventative health supervision visits. The caregiver's sensitive and available supportive role is imperative to establish attachment and the skill set that follows.

Social-emotional developmental phases in healthy children follow a predictable path, therefore tracking these milestones is a crucial component of preventative health supervision visits. For attachment to develop and the ensuing skill set, the caregiver must play a sensitive and accessible supporting role.

At the age of five and six, the child can follow basic guidelines and instructions. They pick up adult social skills like expressing gratitude and offering an apology for inadvertent errors. They relate to a group of pals and prefer to hang out in peer groups more. His imaginative play becomes more intricate, and he enjoys dressing up and putting his fantasies into action. At the age of 7 and 8, the youngster fully comprehends rules and regulations. They can do basic household tasks and exhibit a stronger grasp of relationships and obligations. He gains more sophisticated coping mechanisms and continues to grow morally. A child at this age experiments with new concepts and pursuits, and classmates may challenge his opinions. Children find a best buddy in common and are more able to relate to other kids of the same gender. At the age of 9 and 10, peer and friend groups are more important than family for a child. At this age, children will begin to make more independent decisions and will feel the desire to be independent of their families more and more. Parents can earn time with friends by assigning duties and responsibilities. Self-confidence and self-assurance are developed through a pleasant, loving relationship with a caregiver that is marked by praise and affection, as well as by establishing a healthy balance between independence and home rules. Resilience is increased by encouraging adult connections of support and by providing more possibilities for good community involvement (Malik & Marwaha, 2022).

The failure to meet developmental milestones at the proper age may indicate a psychological issue that requires more investigation. Autism, reactive attachment disorder, social anxiety disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, bullying, oppositional defiant disorder, conduct disorder, and

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

post-traumatic stress disorder are a few examples of early childhood social-emotional disturbance.

In today's ever more diverse world, the classroom is frequently the first setting in which kids interact with individuals with a variety of backgrounds, opinions, and skills. Social and emotional learning (SEL) attempts to help students better understand their thoughts and emotions, to become more self-aware, and to develop more empathy for others in their community and the wider world. This helps account for these differences and help put all students on an equal footing to succeed. In the years to follow, cultivating these traits in the classroom can help kids become better, more productive, self-conscious, and socially aware citizens outside of it.

To foster relationships and help students of different ages find common ground, teachers might choose to assign journaling or writing assignments where students can express their feelings and ideas about a specific SEL topic. Younger students might even be paired with an older class in a "buddy classroom" (or vice versa). Some educators include SEL courses into more traditional topics like reading, arithmetic, and history. Assigning a group project where students self-delegate roles to collaborate for the benefit of the group, having students role-play historical figures to comprehend the motivations behind their actions, or having students conduct formal interviews with one another to gauge current events are a few examples of SEL-in-action.

In this study, the teacher had thought of another way to conduct a social-emotional development learning for the elementary students. To aid the recurring problems both on social-emotional development and reading interest of the learners, the researcher will make use of bibliotherapy. It has been a practice by the researcher to conduct formal bibliotherapy in the classroom, gaining the goal of making an impact in the growth and development of the social and emotional aspect of the learners. It is one of the way on how the teacher connects to his students, in order to show a world through values-integrative stories where they can learn lessons affecting not just their cognitive but as well as their social and emotional development.

When special situations arise, reading books to children is a great method for parents and teachers to connect and reach out. Books' content and narratives can be utilized in education to impart new knowledge, facilitate learning, and exchange experiences for personal development on a wide range of subjects. Parents' assurances sometimes just cannot validate and normalize a child's experience the way books do. A child believes that whatever that is written in a book has to be true. If a topic is worthwhile writing about, it must be significant, at the very least.

Therapy can help young children deal with social-emotional problems, abuse, disabilities, and typical developmental challenges like family conflicts. Bibliotherapy is one method for assisting kids in managing psychological problems. Bibliotherapy, in its most basic definition, is the therapeutic practice of employing books or providing book-related assistance (Pardeck & Pardeck, 1993; Pardeck & Pardeck, 1987).

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Bibliotherapy is the practice of sharing books and other reading materials with children, usually through storytelling, in order to support mental health and assist with emotional issues. Bibliotherapy offers numerous advantages, such as offering understanding and knowledge about issues, raising awareness that others have faced similar issues, promoting conversation about issues, providing solutions to issues, and conveying different attitudes and values. Children can acquire different approaches to and methods of thinking about problems through the use of bibliotherapy. With the help of this technique, kids can learn how to understand themselves and make changes in a safe space to help them deal with emotional stress.

Over the years, bibliotherapy has gone by many names, including library therapeutics, literatherapy, tutorial group therapy, bibliopsychology, biblioeducation, bibliocounseling, and biblioprophylaxis (Pardeck & Pardeck, 1993; Pardeck, 1995). It can be applied as a therapeutic approach to address clinical issues, emotional discomfort in children, minor adjustment issues, and typical growth and adjustment needs. There are three linked goals of bibliotherapy that were proposed by Chatten (1988) identified as: (1) to provide young children the joy and fulfillment that comes from reading; (2) to help them develop a sense of community via reading as a shared activity; and (3) to give them books and someone with whom to read and talk about their concerns.

A variety of developmental problems, including violence, sadness in childhood, and trouble welcoming a new family member into the home, can be treated using bibliotherapy. Children with problems related to their education can benefit from bibliotherapy. Despite the fact that numerous research have revealed that bibliotherapy may not be successful in raising academic attainment. Many authors such as Bauer and Balius, Jr. (1995) and Schrank and Engels (1981) made note of how oral expression and memory abilities are improved as students recount the narrative, and how critical and effective listening skills are formed as the teacher or other professional delivers the story. Having the students write in notebooks or other places about the narrative, their personal experiences, and/or their reactions to it is another common follow-up exercise in bibliotherapy. Students' language and cognitive abilities are strengthened by this regular writing practice.

Given that bibliotherapy makes use of books, it seems sense to believe that it could enhance students' academic performance and learning abilities. On the other hand, not much research has been done on this subject, and what has been done does not support this theory. It is in this note that the researcher would like to expand the sense of using the therapy, trying to address another aspect of human development, which is the social and emotional domains of a child. This study will investigate whether the intervention of using bibliotherapy to improve a child's social and emotional development differs from the impact of a regular classroom session.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Research Questions

This study will have to describe the impact of bibliotherapy to the social-emotional development of the elementary students in Dayton Elementary School, and make some inferential analysis and understanding whether the intervention made a significant difference on this domain before and after the implementation. Hence, the conclusions will also help in identifying how bibliotherapy affects not just academic achievement and learning skills of students, but as well as other human behavior and background.

Specifically, the study seeks to find answers to the following questions:

1. How can the social-emotional development status of the students be described before and after the use of bibliotherapy as an intervention?
2. Is there a significant difference in the the social-emotional state of the students before and after the use of bibliotherapy as an intervention?
3. What are the identified strengths and weaknesses of the application of bibliotherapy as an intervention to improve the social and emotional state of the elementary students?
4. What school bibliotherapy program can be proposed to improve the social and emotional state of the elementary students of San Lorenzo Unified School District?

Hypothesis

In this study, the hypothesis to be tested at 0.05 level of significance is:

Ho: There is no significant difference in the the social and emotional state of the elementary students before and after the use of bibliotherapy as an intervention.

Ha: There is a significant difference in the the social and emotional state of the elementary students before and after the use of bibliotherapy as an intervention.

Significance of the Study

This study finds significance and benefits to the following after the conduct of the study:

To the **elementary students**. The results of this study will open the ideas on embracing the idea of adopting the bibliotherapy as an intervention to address some behavioral, emotional, and the social being of the elementary learners, especially that their stage of life plays a crucial role in intensifying their positivity and thrives. Aside from addressing the real side of a common problem in classroom, which is the difficulty in reading, improving reading comprehension, and enjoying the story reading sessions, the intervention used in this study aimed to develop even the social and emotional side of the students. In this study, it is expected that bibliotherapy connects students' experiences to those of characters facing comparable difficulties, which fosters their resilient thinking, positive feelings, and a sense of belonging. Elementary students will be able to see how

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

the characters handle adversity and deal with unpleasant emotions in a constructive way.

To the **elementary teachers**. One strategy for managing the classroom that teachers might utilize is bibliotherapy, which is the practice of assisting people in growing and developing via literature. in command of the classroom. Hence, the results of the study may not only focus on managing classroom behavior but also, in developing the emotional and social state of the students. Teachers in the elementary level play an important role in nurturing and flourishing the positivity and good social-emotional being of the students. Children's books can be a useful teaching tool for complex topics because they allow readers to relate to the characters on a personal level, which helps them assess their own actions and feelings in light of the experiences of the story's characters. The adaptability of children's literature is one of its advantages. Children's literature is adaptable and can be used to address a wide range of issues that occur in the context of good classroom management.

To the **mental health professionals (including guidance counselors)**. This study will lead them to encourage those who are receiving therapy or are qualified for the therapy to read for developmental objectives, self-help or guidance, information about mental health issues, or just for the therapeutic value of imaginative literature. It has been demonstrated that reading can: normalize encounters with mental health concerns and care; increase the impact of other treatments; assist people comprehend the problems they are facing; and provide hope for positive change. By offering a possible venue for therapeutic activity outside of sessions, bibliotherapy can also hasten and deepen the therapeutic process.

To the **curriculum developers**. Developmental bibliotherapy could have a place in the curriculum. Because trauma is so common and has such a direct impact on learning, we need to consider other strategies to support our young students outside of in-person or in-school therapy sessions. This is especially noteworthy because, in previous years, similar problems were usually ignored. By using Developmental Bibliotherapy with the entire class, students can develop empathy for persons who experience anxiety stemming from traumatic experiences in their early years. In addition, students can learn how to solve problems even if they haven't personally gone through certain kinds of trauma.

To **San Lorenzo Unified School District**. In addition to being utilized with children who are experiencing some sort of hardship, Developmental Bibliotherapy can also be used as a prophylactic tool in educational settings. In order to promote critical thinking and problem solving skills in students as well as awareness, teachers can address typical issues that they encounter in the classrooms of San Lorenzo Unified School District. The said intervention has already been applied and discovered to be impactful by the researcher, thus, he finds it as a good way to improve strategies for teachers in developing the social and emotional aspect of the learners not just on a regular class

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT **Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

education but as well as with the special education classes. The results will benefit the whole district as the researcher would like to develop a comprehensive program of intervention with the use of developmental bibliotherapy to address issues on reading and coherently to affect the social and emotional development of the young learners. It will be a good avenue to produce a clear program that is tested by its effectiveness through a formal research, thus, the intervention requires formal write-up before endorsement to the teachers.

To the **future researchers**. This study will surely help and provide reference and springboard in the development of their future studies especially on bibliotherapy and other topics relation to book therapy or usage.

Scope and Limitations

This study ultimately investigated the effectiveness of using developmental bibliotherapy in promoting social and emotional development to special children with the use of books contextualizing stories and briefly making connections and impacts to inner beings facilitated by the teacher in the classroom. Thus, the results served as basis in endorsing developmental bibliotherapy as an effective program to treat social and emotional issues among the special education learners of Dayton Elementary School, San Lorenzo Unified School District.

The intervention of this study was the bibliotherapy. This covers 10 selected story books shared and read for the students each day of the class. The type of book stories used are delimited to children story books that imposed moral value development to the learners. The list of the books used is on Appendix __. The teacher researcher serves as the reader and the students are the active listeners. The intervention was tested to treat the social-emotional domains of the learners involved in this study.

The participants of the study are the multigrade level (first to third graders) moderate severe, special day class of Dayton Elementary School. It involved a total of ___ elementary special education students. The study is conducted during the school year 2023 – 2024. The application of the intervention was taken and lasted within 20 days interval from each day class session of the teacher-researcher in the classes.

This study will utilize two assessment tools, the pretest and the posttest, covering questions about the social-emotional development status of the learners for the elementary graders for special education class. The tests are delimited to 15 item questions in a likert scale form.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

METHODS OF RESEARCH

This research study utilized a mixed method technique applying experimental approach. The data to be gathered for the experimentation are quantitative in nature, and this study investigated on the effectiveness of the intervention used to treat on the social-emotional domain of the students. The effectiveness was revealed through a comparative analysis on the results of the quantitative data before and after the use of the intervention. Hence, observation procedures were also conducted to gather data on strengths and weaknesses of the intervention used.

Research Design

Quantitative study uses statistical methods to comprehend and interpret phenomena. According to Ary et al. (2010: 26), experimental research entails examining the impact of methodically altering one variable on another. The independent variable, often known as the experimental treatment, is the variable that has been changed.

This study employed the one-group pretest – posttest design experimental approach. Three phases are often involved in the one-group pretest and posttest design: (1) giving the subjects the experimental treatment X, (2) giving the pretest measuring the dependent variable, and (3) giving the subjects the post test, which measures the dependent variable once more. The differences between the pretest and post-test results are then compared in order to assess the effects attributed to the experimental treatment (Creswell, 2020).

In this study, a set of pretest was conducted to identify the descriptives and status of the social-emotional domain of the participants of this study. Afterwards, the bibliotherapy treatment was conducted by the teacher-researcher integrated in the class of the students within a specific time period. Then, a posttest was conducted to measure the dependent variable, which is the social-emotional state of the students, after the intervention treatment. This study further compared the assessed results of the pretest and posttest.

Participants of the Study

The participants of the study were the first to third graders of the special day class, with moderate severe cases, at Dayton Elementary School, San Lorenzo Unified Schools District. The qualification standards for participation lies greatly on the condition that the child was enrolled in the school, under the supervision and monitoring of the teacher-researcher in his class. There was a total of 10 students who were purposively selected to take participation in the study. These students will take participation by answering a self-assessed tool on social-emotional questionnaire.

This study made use of the purposive-total enumeration sampling. According to Dornyei

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

(2007), purposive sampling is a way to choose people who may offer rich and different perspectives into the topic under inquiry. Total population sampling is a type of purposive sampling technique that involves examining the entire population that have a particular set of characteristics (Creswell, 2015).

There are a few reasons why the researcher selected the purposive-total enumeration sampling. The purpose of selection looks down on who qualifies for the perfect fit of the intervention. Bibliotherapy as an intervention fully applies to early ages as it starts developing the reading engagement of the young learners. Also, an extra ounce of intervention is needed to students with special cases and condition, thus, the researcher had thought of using the intervention to learners with moderate severe of special cases so as to help them improve not just the reading and comprehension skills, but as well as their capability to grasp the moral of the stories as they absorb positive drive to achieve a high standard of social-emotional state. Hence, total enumeration sampling was used to cater the needs of all the learners under the moderate severe conditions, securing that no child is left behind, when it comes to the application of academic intervention that helps improve learning conditions and behavioral statuses.

Table 1. Distribution of Participants from Dayton Elementary School

Grade Level	Population	Percent	Sample	Percent
Multigrade Level (Grade 1 – 3)	10	100	10	100
Total	10	100	10	100

Research Instrument

The instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire, covering statements about the social-emotional state of the students. The tool was used both for pre- and post-assessment procedures in order to gather data prior and after the use of the intervention. The tool was developed and patterned from the assessment tool used by Brenchley (2017) in the study titled "Social-Emotional Development Assessment: Scale Development for Kindergarten through Second Grade Youth Universal Screening". The statements were crafted and compressed from a set of items and came up with a comprehensive 15-item assessment tool. The statements developed were patterned from the variables of this study namely (1) self-regulation, (2) emotional regulation, (3) social skills, (4) self-concept, (5) school connectedness or belongingness, (6) social responsibility, and (7) optimism or positivity. The summary of the statements included were assessments on the social-emotional state of the learners that can be shown in the school context.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

To respond on the research questionnaire made by the researcher, the scheme and interpretation below was used:

Scale	Verbal Description
1	Strongly Disagree (SD)
2	Disagree (D)
3	Moderately Agree (MA)
4	Agree (A)
5	Strongly Agree (SA)

Intervention

The proposed intervention in this study was Developmental Bibliotherapy. Developmental Bibliotherapy involves using literature to address emotional, social, or behavioral issues, is a flexible approach that can be adapted to various educational settings, including special education. Special education teachers may use books strategically to support their students' social and emotional development, as well as address specific challenges they may be facing.

Samuel Crothers used the word "bibliotherapy" in 1916 to refer to the use of books in therapy. The Greek words bilion, which means book, and therapeia, which means healing, are the origin of the term. The early 20th century saw the beginning of the recognition of bibliotherapy as a legitimate and significant therapeutic technique in the fields of psychology and psychiatry, with Doctors Karl and William Meninger serving as the therapy's first professional proponents and researchers. Librarians started compiling lists of books that might be therapeutic in the 1930s after realizing that reading might influence a person's ideas, emotions, and behavior. Counselors and librarians started working together at this time, with counselors recommending books to clients who had specific issues.

A variety of developmental problems, including violence, sadness in childhood, and trouble welcoming a new family member into the home, can be treated using bibliotherapy. A list of books with childhood problems like alcohol and drug use, child abuse, values and attitudes, family breakdown, death and dying, peers, school, fears, family struggles, self-image and sex roles, sex education, and special developmental needs was provided by Pardeck and Markward (1995). The specific uses or topics included in the bibliotherapy are education, learning differences, inclusive schools, emotional issues, fear, child abuse, family issues, death, and development.

Children with problems related to their education can benefit from bibliotherapy. Despite the fact that numerous studies have revealed that bibliotherapy may not be successful in its goal to boost academic accomplishment, some authorities on the topic highlight the ways in which bibliotherapy might enhance a student's learning. Numerous writers have noted how oral expression and memory abilities are improved as students recount the narrative, and how critical and effective listening skills are formed as the

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

teacher or other professional delivers the story. Having the students write in notebooks or other places about the narrative, their personal experiences, and/or their reactions to it is another common follow-up exercise in bibliotherapy. Students' language and cognitive abilities are strengthened by this regular writing assignment.

Additionally, bibliotherapy is a useful technique for fostering the intellectual, emotional, and social development of a child (Pardeck & Pardeck, 1990). It is adaptable to each child's developmental stage and requirements for adjustments during development (Pardeck, 1990).

In this study, the flow of implementation of the intervention is described by the diagram below:

The San Lorenzo Unified Schools District and the school where the study was intended to be conducted or implemented were consulted first by the researcher before granting approval. After being permitted, the researcher prepared and produced the assessment tool on social-emotional development of the students at Dayton Elementary School. The researcher used the tool with full guidance and attention to the learners since they are classified with moderate severe special cases. The researcher read each item carefully to the students and let them assess and give themselves their own self-ratings. The rating procedure took twice as it happened before and after the use of the intervention. The assessment procedures took place after __ number of days. The assessment tools were all gathered and recorded for summary to further conduct statistical analyses. Furthermore, the researcher also conducted a thorough observation in order to get answers for the strengths and weaknesses of the intervention during the implementation process. All the gathered information are kept on an archive to secure the student's rights to protection and confidentiality. Hence, the study was conducted with utmost and strict compliance of the Data Privacy Act on schools and students involved in the study.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Data Analysis

To statistically analyze the data gathered, the following formula and interpretation were used:

To compute and describe the current state of social-emotional development of the learner-participants, the mean was used. The formula used was:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

To interpret the mean, the interval of scores and interpretation below was used:

Interval Scores	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low Social-Emotional State
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low Social-Emotional State
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate Social-Emotional State
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High Social-Emotional State
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Social-Emotional State

To determine the effectiveness of the intervention by comparing the pretest and posttest ratings, the t-test paired samples for the difference between means using SPSS was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 alpha level. The mean ratings of the students' level of social-emotional development were compared to test the significant difference before and after the use of the intervention.

To determine the strengths and weaknesses of the use of bibliotherapy, observation was employed by the researcher. All observations were recorded on an observation note and thematic analysis was used to interpret the results from the observed data.

Ethical Considerations

The study participants were contacted by the researcher via a coordinated correspondence letter. The participants were then given a general orientation by the researcher in person during one of the class session. The researcher obtained the students' permission and agreement after being granted permission by the administrators and heads of the school, in accordance with protocol for data collection procedures. The researcher noted that the Data Protection and Privacy Act was strictly followed, and that personal liberty was valued. The researchers themselves had exclusive access to the data that needed to be collected, storing all relevant documents in a confidential archive folder. There was no disclosure of student records in any format. Nonetheless, the survey forms that the teachers completed were created with the highest level of anonymity in mind by omitting the requirement that their names appear on the forms. It was also assured that the outcome of individual assessments does not directly affect the

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

academic standing of the learners, hence, results was used for the exclusive purpose of the study alone. Every outcome was made clear in a finished study report that was sent straight to the district office.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part of the research study shows the explicit results of the questions and the discussions underlying the numerical and observation data.

1. Social-Emotional Development Status of the Elementary Special Students Before and After the Use of Bibliotherapy

During this social-emotional development stage, students are progressively integrating into society. Students transition from total dependence on their parents to a greater level of comfort when dealing with classmates and people outside of their home. Students still need their parents as important attachment figures, but they start to feel more comfortable interacting with others and figuring out what others are feeling (BYJU's Future School, 2022).

Table 2. Social-Emotional Development Status of the Students Before the Use of Bibliotherapy
N = 10

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The student listens to the elders carefully and attentively.	2.63	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
2. The student gets his work done effectively and neatly.	2.70	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
3. The student expresses his feelings well through his actions and behavior.	2.65	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
4. The student can tell how he is feeling about a situation.	2.40	Low Social-Emotional Development

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

5. The student likes to share his own things to others.	2.40	Low Social-Emotional Development
6. The student shows enthusiasm and excitement when talking to others.	2.78	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
7. The student invites and likes playing games with others.	2.55	Low Social-Emotional Development
8. The student approaches other people to ask for help after doing a mistake.	2.28	Low Social-Emotional Development
9. The student feels being included by his friends and classmates in the school.	2.80	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
10. The student likes coming to school.	3.95	High Social-Emotional Development
11. The student receives praises and is admired for his good deeds.	4.00	High Social-Emotional Development
12. The student loves receiving tasks from the teachers and other elders.	3.25	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
13. The student likes helping others in their own ways.	2.50	Low Social-Emotional Development
14. The student does his best when he works.	3.00	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
15. The student has positive attitude and outlook in life.	2.95	Moderate Social-Emotional Development

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Grand Mean	2.86	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
-------------------	------	---------------------------------------

Legend:

Interval Scores	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low Social-Emotional Development
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low Social-Emotional Development
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High Social-Emotional Development
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High Social-Emotional Development

Table 2 shows the social-emotional development status of the multigrade learners of Dayton Elementary School before the intervention on bibliotherapy was used and conducted. The results reveal the computed means and the corresponding verbal interpretations in each indicator statements about the social-emotional state of the learners as perceived by the teachers before being treated with bibliotherapy. Holistically, the development of the learners on this domain clearly reflects through the mean ($\bar{x} = 2.86$) that they have moderate social-emotional development status before the start of the implementation of developmental bibliotherapy.

According to Elias (2022), social-emotional development is as important as cognitively learning the lessons, or even greater. Just as the many cannot expect students to excel in a math class while they are still learning how to add and subtract, it is also not expected for them to show empathy for their classmates when they are still learning how to recognize and express a variety of emotions. Students begin at diverse locations during the early elementary school stage of social and emotional development, but they generally exhibit self-confidence and trust; they think they can achieve and that they can trust people in the classroom and other school-related contexts.

This study clearly justifies the different behaviors exhibited by the learners relating to their social-emotional development status, that may be affected by some factors especially their stay in school. The topmost exhibited behaviors or experiences of the special education students on multigrade levels were: (1) the student receives praises and is admired for his good deeds ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), high social-emotional development status; (2) the student likes coming to school ($\bar{x} = 3.95$), high social-emotional development status; (3) the student loves receiving tasks from the teachers and other elders ($\bar{x} = 3.25$), moderate social-emotional development status; (4) the student does his best when he works ($\bar{x} = 3.00$), moderate social-emotional development status; and (5) the student has positive attitude and outlook in life ($\bar{x} = 2.95$), moderate social-emotional development status.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Children's social and emotional development can be effectively supported by providing them with meaningful feedback in the form of effective praise that is relevant to the job at hand (Kostelnik et al. 2015). Teachers who use particular descriptions of what they observe, without generalizing, assessing, or drawing comparisons are able to effectively praise the students. Early childhood educators must show warmth and affection to children, especially on difficult days and during misbehavior.

On the other hand, the least developed social-emotional skills of the elementary graders under the special education program of Dayton Elementary School were: (1) the student approaches other people to ask for help after doing a mistake ($\bar{x} = 2.28$), low social-emotional development status; (2) the student can tell how he is feeling about a situation ($\bar{x} = 2.40$), low social-emotional development status; (3) the student likes to share his own things to others ($\bar{x} = 2.40$), low social-emotional development status; (4) the student likes helping others in their own ways ($\bar{x} = 2.50$), low social-emotional development status; and (5) the student invites and likes playing games with others ($\bar{x} = 2.55$), low social-emotional development status.

Other critical Social-Emotional learning development are directly associated with teaching students to accept responsibility for their errors. This study discloses the weakness of the learners on asking for help especially after committing a mistake. This is a crucial part of social-emotional learning because it teaches students to accept responsibility for their own mistakes, remain composed, and tell the truth. Students who master these abilities will be able to grow into more responsible and accountable adults by learning from their failures.

Table 3. Social-Emotional Development Status of the Students After the Use of Bibliotherapy
N = 10

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. The student listens to the elders carefully and attentively.	2.80	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
2. The student gets his work done effectively and neatly.	2.90	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
3. The student expresses his feelings well through his actions and behavior.	3.03	Moderate Social-Emotional Development

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

4. The student can tell how he is feeling about a situation.	2.65	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
5. The student likes to share his own things to others.	2.83	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
6. The student shows enthusiasm and excitement when talking to others.	3.23	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
7. The student invites and likes playing games with others.	2.93	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
8. The student approaches other people to ask for help after doing a mistake.	2.63	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
9. The student feels being included by his friends and classmates in the school.	3.20	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
10. The student likes coming to school.	3.95	High Social-Emotional Development
11. The student receives praises and is admired for his good deeds.	4.00	High Social-Emotional Development
12. The student loves receiving tasks from the teachers and other elders.	3.30	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
13. The student likes helping others in their own ways.	3.08	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
14. The student does his best when he works.	3.13	Moderate Social-Emotional Development

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

15. The student has positive attitude and outlook in life.	3.00	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
Grand Mean	3.11	Moderate Social-Emotional Development

Legend:

Interval Scores	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low Social-Emotional Development
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low Social-Emotional Development
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate Social-Emotional Development
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High Social-Emotional Development
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High Social-Emotional Development

On table 3, means were computed out of the assessed ratings by the teachers on their students' social-emotional development after the immediate use of the bibliotherapy as an intervention. Findings reveal the grand mean on the rating of the students' assessed social-emotional development was 3.11, indicative of a moderate social-emotional development. In terms of verbal descriptions, the conditions were all the same, having a moderate case of showcasing social-emotional development by the learners. However, the difference between means shows a significant increase of 0.25 value.

Table 3 clearly shows the computed means and corresponding verbal interpretations in each of the indicators on social-emotional development of the students after the implementation of bibliotherapy. The top three exhibited behaviors or experiences of the special education students on multigrade levels after the use of the intervention were still the same that is: (1) the student receives praises and is admired for his good deeds ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), high social-emotional development status; (2) the student likes coming to school ($\bar{x} = 3.95$), high social-emotional development status; (3) the student loves receiving tasks from the teachers and other elders ($\bar{x} = 3.30$), moderate social-emotional development. Additional to the set of behaviors exemplified by the students were: (4) the student shows enthusiasm and excitement when talking to others ($\bar{x} = 3.23$), moderate social-emotional development; and (5) the student feels being included by his friends and classmates in the school ($\bar{x} = 3.23$), moderate social-emotional development.

On the other note, the social-emotional indicators that were least observed by the teachers to their students even after the use of the intervention were the following: (1) the student approaches other people to ask for help after doing a mistake ($\bar{x} = 2.63$), moderate social-emotional development status; (2) the student can tell how he is feeling

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

about a situation ($\bar{x} = 2.65$), moderate social-emotional development status; (3) the student listens to the elders carefully and attentively ($\bar{x} = 2.80$), moderate social-emotional development status; (4) the student likes to share his own things to others ($\bar{x} = 2.83$), moderate social-emotional development status; and (5) the student invites and likes playing games with others ($\bar{x} = 2.93$), moderate social-emotional development status. Perceivably, most of the indicators were almost increased as rated by the teachers, showing that there were no interpreted as “low social-emotional development status”. All these low levels were converted into “moderate social-emotional development status” after the use of bibliotherapy.

In the study of Payton, et.al. (2008) about the impacts of social-emotional learning for kindergarten to eight-grade students, social-emotional treatments proved successful for students with and without presenting issues, in both classroom and after-school environments. They were also effective for K–8 grade levels, urban, suburban, and rural schools, and student bodies with a variety of racial and ethnic backgrounds.

2. Significant Difference in the Social-Emotional State of the Students Before and After the Use of Bibliotherapy

Table 4. T-Test Results

Test	t-value	p-value	Level of Significance	Degrees of Freedom	Decision	Interpretation
t-test	2.144	0.000	0.05	14	Reject null hypothesis	Difference is significant at 0.05

Table 4 shows the results of the hypothesis testing. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 alpha level, revealing that the computed t-value from the data gathered was 2.144 with a p-value of approximately 0.000. This significantly clears out the idea of rejecting the null hypothesis as a decision, since the computed p-value ($p = 0.000$) is less than the alpha level set ($\alpha = 0.05$). This further defines that the difference between the pretest and posttest ratings of the students on social-emotional development status was found statistically significant. It further means to say that, the intervention which is bibliotherapy made a significant impact in changing the level of social-emotional development status of the students, through the effective use of book therapy.

As a result, bibliotherapy makes a significant change and impact to the social-emotional domain of the learners. This is rooted from the moral values and explicit ethics and principles shared and was explained by the chosen stories to the mind of the young learners. Reading should not only enhance the comprehension of the learners, but this

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

study also proves that acquired moral standards can also be upgraded through a sensible and active listening methods by the students.

3. Strengths and Weaknesses of the Application of Bibliotherapy as an Intervention to Improve the Social-Emotional Development of the Elementary Special Students

The results on the strengths and weaknesses of the application of bibliotherapy greatly relies on the observation and experiences of the teacher during its implementation in special education classes of multigrade levels. Multigrade levels offer a variety of experiences and expose a great difference on learning approaches of the learners due to their deep personal backgrounds, diverse needs, and levels of understanding and maturity due to their specific relative cases.

One of the strengths of bibliotherapy is the enhanced love for reading. The love for reading is still a battle cry for many elementary teachers, as this stage start up the cultivation on the widening of vocabularies among the learners. It also helps the value formation as stories always share a sentimental change on the perspective of life, especially at a young age, when learners start to visualize ideas on moral discernment and think on a high standard of community and social ethics.

The intervention also promoted social development. It was observed that it reduced the feelings of isolation that may be felt by the students who were encountering sadness or insecurities. The product of the intervention made the students to become more socially aware and promote inclusion especially on group sessions conducted by the teacher.

Other strengths of bibliotherapy are its nobility and flexibility as a method. Physical interaction with the students while doing bibliotherapy lets the teacher explore more about the children. It can be delivered for an individualized intervention or may even be applied for a group of students. When utilizing bibliotherapy with a group of kids, playing back the tale on a tape recorder can be a useful method as opposed to reading the book aloud to them or having them read it on their own. This enables the therapist to pause the video at certain times in the story for conversation and to observe the children's nonverbal reactions. The flexibility on the method is not delimited to the process of reading by saying the words aloud during the sessions. Group bibliotherapy has the benefit of allowing the kids to "piggyback" on each other's ideas, resulting in a multitude of creative solutions.

Also, the availability of materials to be used were not a necessary hindrance on the implementation since there are numerous of stories and books available to be retrieved for implementation, thus, the coverage of the context on nurturing the behavioral patterns based on the stories must always be checked through the alignment of what behavioral change is expected to occur. Not all materials treat a human behavior holistically. Specially when dealing with social-emotional development, the

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

materials are needed to be assessed so as to achieve the goal on making a behavioral change brought about by the contexts of the selections and stories.

On the other hand, weaknesses or disadvantages also showed up during implementation. A part of the reading process and dilemma by most of the teachers is the signs of distress among the students during the reading sessions. These scenarios bring the teacher to fuel up and start innovating the strategies to regain the students' excitement for reading. It is best to cease reading to a kid right once if they exhibit signs of discomfort or boredom; they might not be ready for bibliotherapy, or the books they are reading might need to be changed.

Another disadvantage on taking bibliotherapy to a group of learners is the diversity on viewpoints and miscues on the understanding of the context. One secret technique of the teacher must be a clear review of the meanings and context of the stories, before delivering it and creating new forms of knowledge. A crucial component of bibliotherapy is discussion. Following the child's reading of the literature, the facilitator and the child should discuss the tale and its consequences. The adult should also assist the child in thinking through their responses to the book. Taking reactions from the students must be greatly considered through affirmations and positive interactions.

It has also been observed that students find it easier to discuss the emotions of the character rather than their own feelings most of the time. It creates a difficulty on the side of the teacher to facilitate and engage the own feelings of the students if they will continuously drag themselves off their own perspective. Hence, this also exposes the unveiling of the difficulty of the teachers to let the students freely express their thoughts and get involved in this behavioral therapy.

Lastly, the teacher's skill as a facilitator can also be a challenge. It is possible that facilitators possess insufficient understanding of human development, developmental issues, and relevant literature. As a result, facilitators must receive the appropriate training and exposure to a wide range of books that are appropriate for bibliotherapy. Another drawback of bibliotherapy could be inherent in the method itself: for instance, clients might not want to talk about topics that make them uncomfortable, or facilitators might insist on proving a point at the expense of the client.

4. Proposed School Bibliotherapy Program

Table 5. Proposed School Bibliotherapy Program

Phases	Intervention/ Activities/ Strategies	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Persons Involved	Success Indicator
Skill Orientation and Capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The district administrators or school head conducts a 	Before the start of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biblio-therapists Resource Speaker 	District Administrat or	The school head conducted a training

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Building on Bibliotherapy	capacity-building training program about bibliotherapy.	school year	(Psychologist/ Psychiatrist) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Materials such as pamphlets and Books on Bibliotherapy 	School Head School Psychologists Teachers	program and is attended by at least 80% of the teachers
Crafting of the Individualized Bibliotherapy Implementation Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers will craft their own implementation plan of the program and submit it to the school head or district office 	First month of the school year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Books to be used in bibliotherapy • Printing materials 	District Administrator or School Head School Teachers	The teacher completely submits their accomplished individualized bibliotherapy implementation plan
Problem Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The teacher conducts surveys on the learners through profiling or personal interviews 	First quarter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey • Profiles and records of the Students • Social-Emotional Development Checklist 	Teachers Students	The teacher completed a survey and accomplished the social-emotional development rating scale
Catharsis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Child involvement on seeing similarities between his or her problem and the book character's problem. 	Year-round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Books • Diaries • Behavioral Assessment Tools 	Teachers Students Behavioral Health Professionals	The teachers were able to deliver a complete set of 50 stories year-round and students are able to share connections to the stories.
Development of Solutions and Alternatives to Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Story-telling and sharing • Voice tape recording 	Year-round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Books • Voice tapes • Diaries 	Teachers Students Behavioral Health	The student could retell the plot and discuss the situations,

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

**WORLD
EDUCATION
CONNECT**
MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-verbal communications and Reactions • Diary writing • Generalizations and conclusions 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral Assessment Tools 	Professionals	characters, and feelings that are depicted in the book. The students can answer the questions about the stories correctly.
Follow-up Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drawing • Painting • Collages • Family Trees • Clay Figures • Dramatizations • Puppetry • Pantomiming • Writing 	Year-round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drawing Materials • Art Materials • Clays • Props • Puppets 	Teachers Students Behavioral Health Professionals	The students effectively expressed themselves through the alternative activities.
Post-assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-testing 	End of school year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posttest materials 	Teachers Students Behavioral Health Professionals	The students were able to be assessed based on a defined behavioral rating tool on social-emotional development

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This part of the research presents the synthesized general understanding and findings of the study, conclusions formulated based on the findings, and the recommendations drawn from the conclusions.

Summary of Findings

On this part, the findings of the study were summarized as follows:

1. The computed mean ($\bar{x} = 2.86$) of the level of social-emotional development before the use of bibliotherapy indicates moderate social-emotional development.
2. The computed mean ($\bar{x} = 3.11$) of the level of social-emotional development after the use of bibliotherapy indicates moderate social-emotional development.
3. The topmost exhibited behaviors or experiences of the special education students on multigrade levels before the use of intervention were: (1) the student receives praises and is admired for his good deeds ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), high social-emotional development status; (2) the student likes coming to school ($\bar{x} = 3.95$), high social-emotional development status; (3) the student loves receiving tasks from the teachers and other elders ($\bar{x} = 3.25$), moderate social-emotional development status; (4) the student does his best when he works ($\bar{x} = 3.00$), moderate social-emotional development status; and (5) the student has positive attitude and outlook in life ($\bar{x} = 2.95$), moderate social-emotional development status.
4. The least developed social-emotional skills of the elementary graders under the special education program of Dayton Elementary School before the use of the intervention were: (1) the student approaches other people to ask for help after doing a mistake ($\bar{x} = 2.28$), low social-emotional development status; (2) the student can tell how he is feeling about a situation ($\bar{x} = 2.40$), low social-emotional development status; (3) the student likes to share his own things to others ($\bar{x} = 2.40$), low social-emotional development status; (4) the student likes helping others in their own ways ($\bar{x} = 2.50$), low social-emotional development status; and (5) the student invites and likes playing games with others ($\bar{x} = 2.55$), low social-emotional development status.
5. The top three exhibited behaviors or experiences of the special education students on multigrade levels after the use of the intervention were still the same that is: (1) the student receives praises and is admired for his good deeds ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), high social-emotional development status; (2) the student likes coming to school ($\bar{x} = 3.95$), high social-emotional development status; (3) the student loves receiving tasks from the teachers and other elders ($\bar{x} = 3.30$), moderate social-emotional development. Additional to the set of behaviors

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

- exemplified by the students were: (4) the student shows enthusiasm and excitement when talking to others ($\bar{x} = 3.23$), moderate social-emotional development; and (5) the student feels being included by his friends and classmates in the school ($\bar{x} = 3.23$), moderate social-emotional development.
6. The social-emotional indicators that were least observed by the teachers to their students even after the use of the intervention were the following: (1) the student approaches other people to ask for help after doing a mistake ($\bar{x} = 2.63$), moderate social-emotional development status; (2) the student can tell how he is feeling about a situation ($\bar{x} = 2.65$), moderate social-emotional development status; (3) the student listens to the elders carefully and attentively ($\bar{x} = 2.80$), moderate social-emotional development status; (4) the student likes to share his own things to others ($\bar{x} = 2.83$), moderate social-emotional development status; and (5) the student invites and likes playing games with others ($\bar{x} = 2.93$), moderate social-emotional development status. Perceivably, most of the indicators were almost increased as rated by the teachers, showing that there were no interpreted as "low social-emotional development status".
 7. The computed t-value from the data gathered was 2.144 with a p-value of approximately 0.000.

Conclusions

On this part, the conclusions formulated from the analysis of data conducted were:

1. All these low levels were converted into "moderate social-emotional development status" after the use of bibliotherapy.
2. Since the computed p-value ($p = 0.000$) is less than the alpha level set ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. It means that the difference between the pretest and posttest ratings of the students on social-emotional development status was found statistically significant. It further means that the intervention which is bibliotherapy made a significant impact in changing the level of social-emotional development status of the students, through the effective use of book therapy.
3. The observed strengths of the use of bibliotherapy were as follows:
 - 3.1. Students enhanced their love for reading.
 - 3.2. The intervention promoted social development among the students.
 - 3.3. Bibliotherapy are its nobility and flexibility as a method. It can be delivered for an individualized intervention or may even be applied for a group of students.
 - 3.4. The availability of materials for bibliotherapy is sufficient.
4. The observed weaknesses of the use of bibliotherapy were as follows:

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

-
- 4.1. A part of the reading process and dilemma by most of the teachers is the signs of distress among the students during the reading sessions.
 - 4.2. Taking bibliotherapy to a group of learners leads to diversity of viewpoints and miscues on the understanding of the context.
 - 4.3. Teacher's skill as a facilitator can also be a challenge.

Recommendations

This part states the recommendations drawn and endorsed, thus, being summarized as follows:

1. The district administrators may initiate and conduct a seminar training program or capacity building on school bibliotherapy program.
2. The school heads may ask their teachers to prepare their individualized classroom bibliotherapy implementation plan and extend technical assistance on its implementation.
3. Behavioral health professionals may facilitate trainings on bibliotherapy for better program outcomes and implementation.
4. Parents may also adopt procedures on bibliotherapy for home remedies on behavioral corrections among their children.
5. School psychologists may use the data on bibliotherapy in promoting better programs and develop better intervention plans relative to bibliotherapy.
6. Schools may invest on books that imposes bibliotherapeutic treatments developing social-emotional domains of the students.
7. Researchers may use the results of this study for reference to future similar studies.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, M. (2005). What is bibliotherapy? Retrieved from: <https://cyc-net.org/cyc-online/cycol-0105-biblio.html#:~:text=Benefits%20and%20limitations%20of%20bibliotherapy&text=It%20reduces%20feelings%20of%20isolation,readiness%20and%20willingness%20to%20read.>
- Adderholdt-Elliott, M., & Eller, S.H. (1989). Counseling students who are gifted through bibliotherapy. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 22 (1), 26-31.
- Brenchley, A. (2017). Social-Emotional Development Assessment: Scale Development for Kindergarten through Second Grade Youth Universal Screening.
- Dunne, L. (2020). Middle School Educator's Views of Bibliotherapy: Using Books as Healing Tools to Help Adolescents Navigate Problematic Issues: A Case Study. St. John's University, New York. Retrieved from: https://scholar.stjohns.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1074&context=theses_dissertations
- Early Childhood Learning & Knowledge Center (2021). Social and Emotional Development. Retrieved from : <https://eclkc.ohs.acf.hhs.gov/school-readiness/effective-practice-guides/social-emotional-development>
- Eisenman, G & Harper, R. (2016). Bibliotherapy for Classroom Management. *Dimensions of Early Childhood*. 44(1). Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1150264.pdf>
- Elias, M. (2022). How Students Typically Grow in SEL From Elementary to Middle School. *Edutopia*. Retrieved from: <https://www.edutopia.org/article/how-students-typically-grow-sel-elementary-middle-school/>
- Ho, J. & Funk, S. (2018). Promoting Young Children's Social and Emotional Health. *National Association for the Education of Young Children*, 73 (1). Retrieved from: <https://www.naeyc.org/resources/pubs/yc/mar2018/promoting-social-and-emotional-health>
- Johnston, K. et.al., (2000). *Learning & Growing Together: Understanding Your Child's Development*. Washington, D.C.: ZERO TO THREE
- Lee, K. (2021). When Your Child Makes a Mistake: How you react to your child's setbacks can have a surprising effect. Retrieved from: <https://www.verywellfamily.com/what-to-do-when-your-child-makes-a-mistake-4050012>
- Ludwig, Lisa, "An overview of bibliotherapy as an intervention for young children" (2002). *Graduate Research Papers*. 1129. <https://scholarworks.uni.edu/grp/1129>
- Maich, K. & Kean, S. (2004). Read two books and write me in the morning: Bibliotherapy for social emotional intervention in the inclusive classroom. *TEACHING Exceptional Children Plus*, 1(2). Retrieved from: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ966510>

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

-
- Malik, F. & Marwaha, R. (2022). Developmental Stages of Social Emotional Development in Children. National Library of Medicine, National Center for Biotechnology Information. Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK534819/>
- McCulliss, D. & Chamberlain, D. (2013). Bibliotherapy for youth and adolescents- school-based application and research. *Journal of Poetry Therapy: The Interdisciplinary Journal of Practice, Theory, Research and Education*, 26(1), 13-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08893675.2013.764052>
- Melnick, H. & Martinez L. (2019). How One Elementary School Integrates Social-Emotional Skills in the Classroom. Berkeley University of California. Retrieved from: https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/article/item/how_one_elementary_school_integrates_social_emotional_skills_in_the_classro
- National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (2024). What is one way that SEL is showing up in elementary school(s) in your context?. Retrieved from: <https://safesupportivelearning.ed.gov/voices-field/what-one-way-sel-showing-elementary-schools-your-context>
- National University (2024). What is Social Emotional Learning (SEL): Why it Matters. San Diego, CA. Retrieved from: <https://www.nu.edu/blog/social-emotional-learning-sel-why-it-matters-for-educators/>
- Nelson, J., Erwin, C. & Duffy, R. (2007). *Positive Discipline: The First Three Years*. New York, NY: Three Rivers Press.
- Pardeck, J. T., & Pardeck, J. A. (1993). *Bibliotherapy. A clinical approach for helping children*. New York, NY: Gordon and Breach Science.
- Payton, J. et.al. (2008). *The Positive Impact of Social and Emotional Learning for Kindergarten to Eight-Grade Students: Findings from three scientific reviews*. Chicago, IL: Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED505370.pdf>
- Reinsberg, K. (2020). *Social and Emotional Development: What is Social-Emotional Development?*. AbilityPath, Redwood City, CA. Retrieved from: <https://abilitypath.org/ap-resources/what-is-social-emotional-development/>
- Tijms, J., Stoop, M.A. & Pollock, J.N. (2018). Bibliotherapeutic book club intervention to promote reading skills and social-emotional competencies in low SES community-based high schools: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 41(3), 525-545. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9817.12123>
- Virtual Lab School (2023). *Social-Emotional Development: An Introduction*. Retrieved from: <https://www.virtuallabschool.org/preschool/social-and-emotional-development/lesson-1>

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

LIST OF BOOKS USED IN BIBLIOTHERAPY

- Cook, Julia. (2016). *The Judgmental Flower (Building Relationships)*. Boys Town Press.
- Crow, Caroline (2017). *Tiny Tantrum*. Tiger Tales.
- Dakos, Kalli. (2017). *Why Am I Blue? A Story About Being Yourself*. YouthLight Inc.
- Dean, Karen. (2011). *She Said What About Me? Hurtful Words Can Destroy a Special Friendship*. YouthLight Inc.
- Doleski, Teddi. (1987). *The Hurt: Letting Go of Hurt Feelings*. Paulist Press.
- Gibb, C. (2022). *A Sky of Diamonds: A Story for Children About Loss, Grief and Hope*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- John, J., & Oswald, P. (2019). *The Good Egg (First edition.)*. Harper, an imprint of HarperCollins Publishers.
- Lambert, T., & Napoli, E. (2020). *Why Do I Feel So Sad? A Grief Book For Children*. Rockridge Press.
- Marcus, A. M. (2015). *The Carrot, the Egg and the Tea Bag*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Masurel, C., & Denton, K. M. (2001). *Two Homes*. Cambridge, MA, Candlewick Press.
- McCloud, C., & Messing, D. (2006). *Have You Filled A Bucket Today? A Guide To Daily Happiness For Kids*. Northville, Michigan, Ferne Press.
- Meiners, C. J., & Johnson, M. (2010). *Cool Down and Work Through Anger*. Minneapolis, MN, Free Spirit Pub.
- Metzger, S. & Cain, J. (2021) *The Way I Act*. Seattle, USA, Washington: Parenting Press, Incorporated.
- Morin, A., & Joseph, J, (2020) *What is Empathy? A Bullying Storybook for Kids*. Rockridge Press.
- Parr, Todd. "It's Okay to Be different." New York: Little, Brown, 2009, 2001.
- Parr, Todd. (2019). *The Don't Worry Book (First edition.)*. Little, Brown and Company.
- Vandawalker, M. (2008). *What Color Are Tears?* YouthLight
- Pett, M., & Rubinstein, G. (2011). *The Girl Who Never Made Mistakes*. Naperville, Ill., Sourcebooks Jabberwocky.
- Richards, M. (2014). *I Didn't Know I Was Bully!* MarCo Products
-

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.
Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue III (March 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Schaub, M. (2021). *Kindness is a Kite String: The Uplifting Power of Empathy*. Cardinal Rule Press

Sileo, F. J., & Pillo, C. (2013). *Sally Sore Loser: A Story About Winning and Losing*. Washington, DC, Magination Press.

Sunderland, M. (2003). *How Hattie Hated Kindness: A Story for Children Locked in Rage of Hate*. Speechmark Publishing Ltd.

Weisberg, R., (2022). *The Unique Beetle: An Empowering Self-esteem Book for Kids*. Reut Weisberg

Weisberg, S., (2022). *Am I Happy? A Book for Kids about Finding Your Happiness and Appreciating What You Have*. Shahr Weisberg

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10874106

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.